

Polymeric Materials in Municipal Water Treatment

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Manuscript received 1 November 1976, revised 13 June 1977, accepted 3 October 1977

The efficiency of cationic, anionic, non-ionic polyelectrolytes as aid to coagulation of colloidal water can be increased by the use of fly ash (<100 mesh), alum sludge (<1 hr. aged sample) and activated carbon. Reduction of bacteria in the clarified water is an additional advantage using these polyelectrolytes along with fly-ash/alum sludge/activated carbon in the alum treatment process.

Polyelectrolytic behaviour of soil humic and humatomelanic acids were utilized in this connection for clarification of river water along with alum.

RECENT years have witnessed the introduction of a number of synthetic polyelectrolytes in water treatment process¹. Natural polymers like humic acid, humatomelanic acid etc. possess polyelectrolyte character^{2,3}.

An attempt has been made here to find out whether betterment in respect of coagulation and flocculation of turbid water could be made with the simultaneous use of certain polymeric materials including humic and humatomelanic acids and fly-ash/alum sludge, activated carbon along with prime coagulant alum.

Materials and Methods

River water samples were collected from a fixed depth of basin (0 to 4 ft) near Palta Water (PWW), Barrackpore throughout the representative seasons of the year and the study continued for two consecutive years i.e. 1971-72 and 1972-73. All the studies were made according to Adhikari et al⁴. The coagulation phenomenon was studied thoroughly in 'Jar Test Apparatus' as prescribed by American Public Health Association⁴. The following conditions in Jar Test were maintained :

Speed : 30 to 40 RPM
Flocculation Time : 20 minutes
Settling Time : 10 minutes
Volume of sample in each jar : 910 ml. sequence of addition : First polymeric material, then alum.

The following polyelectrolytes were used in this study :

(a) Cationic : Polyacrylamide (PAAm)

Acrylamide was polymerized in aqueous solution at 60° using $K_2S_2O_8$ as initiator and the polymer was precipitated by acetone as non solvent and dried under vacuum.

(b) Anionic : Sodium polyacrylate (SPAA) and sodium carboxymethyl Cellulose (SCMC)

Polyacrylic acid was prepared by thermal polymerization of acrylic acid using benzoyl peroxide as initiator. Sodium carboxymethyl cellulose was supplied by Chemmet, India.

(c) Non-ionic

Polyethylene glycol (PEG) was supplied by Union Carbide. Humic acid and humatomelanic acid and their respective sodium salts were prepared according to Adhikari et al⁴ and Ghosh et al³.

In actual experiment all the polyelectrolytes were added in a fixed dosage of 0.5 mg per litre of turbid water and for fly-ash, alum-sludge and activated carbon, amounts applied were 500 mg, 250 mg and 100 mg respectively per litre of river water. Humic acid, humatomelanic acid and their sodium salts were applied at a dosage of 1.5 mg/litre. These dosages were determined from preliminary experiment to get the maximum possible reduction of prime coagulant (with close approximation) with water of turbidity 1000 p.p.m.

Results and Discussion

The average physicochemical characteristics of the Ganges water samples are given elsewhere⁵. The analysis of fly-ash is given in our earlier communications⁶. Activated carbon used was of the following characteristics : 100% through 100 mesh, weight : 22 to 25 mg/100 ml suspendibility : 65%, carbon content : 75% and moisture : 5.5%.

A comparative study of the coagulating characteristics of polycationic (i.e. PAAm) and alum is made in terms of residual turbidity of treated water against the addition of addendas and is shown in Fig. 1(a). The curve for the former is steeper in comparison to the latter and is considered as due to stronger enmeshment of polyelectrolytes and clay in

the flocculation phase. Polycationic actually has prevented any carry over¹¹ of soluble Al₂O₃.

Fig. 1(a)

Table 1 shows the effectiveness in coagulation and floc formation of PAAm, SPAA, SCMC and PEG in presence of ash along with basic alum for limiting coagulation. The following order was observed in terms of extent of diminution of original alum dosage : SPAA > SCMC > PAAm > PEG. Similar order was noticed when alum sludge and activated carbon were used instead of ash, although activated carbon itself is a good adjunct to flocculation, because of its superior adsorption capacity. The laboratory experimentations with polymeric materials were extended to plant scale study to justify the suitability. Both the samples, one anionic (caflo) and the other a mixture of cationic, anionic and non-ionic (polymers) were supplied by the private houses viz. Product Development Council, Panihati and Jalan Enterprise. The results of the experiments are given below :

TABLE :—1 (A) FOR OPTICAL CLARIFICATION

Name of Polymer	Initial Turbidity of River Water in p.p.m.	Actual alum requirement in g.p.g	Requirement of alum along with the polymer in g.p.g	Dosage of polymer along with alum in p.p.m.
CAFLO	800	2.0	1.00	0.1
Polymix	1200	3.2	1.00	0.05

The exact constitution and nature of polymers were not supplied by the suppliers to maintain their trade secrecy. Both the products were not verified by 'Toxicity Test', hence those were not recommended for daily application, although the mechanism of polymeric action was well supported. The point of application was the clariflocculation plant drawing approximately 12 million gallon of river water per day. The superior clarifying capacity of the anions is due to their high molecular weight and degree of polymerization⁷. The anionic polymers help to shift (ξ -potential to the electronegative direction and such undesirable shift of) ξ -potential is counterbalanced, simultaneously by their capacity to attach several microfloc particles resulting in a mechanical and electrical interlocking⁸.

Fig. 1(b) represents the characteristics of 3-type of polyelectrolytes as aids to either coagulation or flocculation. Both cationic and anionic aids beyond the optimum dosage for coagulation effect 'charge reversal' and sometimes undesirable shift of potential which cause deflocculation of floc particles. The non-ionic PEG, however, can not cause potential change after the addition of the same beyond optimum dosage and thus this curve becomes parallel^{7,9} after the optimal dosage.

Fig. 1(b)

The mechanism of coagulation and flocculation by polyelectrolytes⁸ has been verified from the viscometric study of clay~SCMC interaction (Fig. 1c). Here non dialysed river clay~SCMC interaction in terms of η vs t is shown the steeper portion (minimum slope of the curve) represent the zone of SCMC clay interaction which obviates coagulation. This is also evident from the figure where subsequent rise in curve is shown just after the interaction. The interactions in three types of Clay-Al—Poly are identical eg. as Clay-Al-HA (Greenland¹⁰) [Al= Aluminium ion, Poly=polyelectrolyte, HA=humic

TABLE—1 INFLUENCE OF DIFFERENT POLYELECTROLYTES IN PRESENCE/ABSENCE OF ASH/SLUDGE/CARBON IN REDUCTION OF ALUM DOSAGE AND BACTERIAL POPULATION (MPN)

Turbidity of Samples in p.p.m.	Alum (alone) in p.p.m.	0.5 p.p.m. SPAA only	Alum required for optimal coagulation with						0.5 p.p.m. PAAM+ 500 p.p.m. ash
			0.5 p.p.m. SCMC only	0.5 p.p.m. PAAM only	0.5 p.p.m. PEG only	0.5 p.p.m. SPAA+ 500 p.p.m. ash	0.5 p.p.m. SCMC+ 500 p.p.m. ash		
817	36.40	25.00	25.00	28.00	32.00	21.05	22.50	25.00	
984	35.70	25.00	26.00	27.00	31.00	21.50	23.75	26.00	
1000	37.80	26.00	29.00	32.00	33.25	25.85	27.35	29.00	
1083	42.00	31.00	35.25	38.00	39.00	25.00	27.00	30.00	
1108	50.80	32.25	38.25	40.00	46.60	26.50	28.00	32.28	
1600	56.00	44.00	46.00	49.35	52.00	43.00	45.17	47.39	
1700	58.00	46.83	49.00	51.35	55.90	44.50	46.07	49.00	

0.5 p.p.m. PEG + 500 p.p.m. ash	0.5 p.p.m. SPAA + 250 p.p.m. Sludge	0.5 p.p.m. SCMC + 250 p.p.m. Sludge	Alum required for optimal coagulation with				0.5 p.p.m. SCMC + 100 p.p.m. carbon	0.5 p.p.m. PAAM + 100 p.p.m. carbon	0.5 p.p.m. PEG + 100 p.p.m. carbon
			0.5 p.p.m. PAAM + 250 p.p.m. Sludge	0.5 p.p.m. PEG + 250 p.p.m. Sludge	0.5 p.p.m. SPAA + 100 p.p.m. carbon	0.5 p.p.m. PAAM + 100 p.p.m. carbon			
28.10	25.50	26.95	28.00	30.25	19.25	21.00	22.50	25.35	
29.00	29.00	29.00	30.15	32.00	19.00	21.00	23.00	27.00	
30.28	28.50	30.25	32.45	35.00	20.50	22.00	24.80	28.47	
32.00	30.19	31.13	33.56	36.21	20.00	23.25	25.61	29.25	
33.61	30.32	31.05	34.13	37.50	20.25	24.90	27.00	30.13	
50.12	45.00	46.12	48.25	50.16	37.05	39.21	40.98	42.13	
52.11	47.37	47.85	50.49	51.16	41.25	43.17	45.23	46.80	

Turbidity in p.p.m.	Alum (alone) in p.p.m.	Bacterial population (i.e. MPN) in different treatment x 10 ⁻⁸ /100 ml _g				MPN in Alum (only) treated/100 ml
		Alum + 0.5 p.p.m. SPAA + 500 p.p.m. ash	Alum + 0.5 p.p.m. SCMC + 500 p.p.m. ash	Alum + 0.5 p.p.m. PAAM + 500 p.p.m. ash	Alum + 0.5 p.p.m. PEG + 500 p.p.m. ash	
(A) 1000	37.80	0.025	0.040	0.080	0.720	0.09
(B) 1200	40.50	0.012	0.020	0.050	0.430	0.06
(C) 1400	50.50	0.080	0.100	0.130	0.140	0.15

acids like humic, fulvic and hylatomelanic acid etc.] The higher flocculating capacity of non-ionic PEG is probably due to ready hydration of hydrophilic molecular like other non-ionic⁷. n_{sp}/conc vs. n_{sp} curve is (Fig. 1c) slightly different from that of dialysed clay interaction and is due to presence of non clayey materials in the raw water.

Fig. 1(c)

The studies with humic acids along with SPAA as a model system are shown in Table 2. From the

comparison of nature of settling and floc formation capacity by the three sodium salts of humic acids fractions it appears that they may be placed in the order: SPAA > NaHyA > NaHA. The superior flocculating character of NaHyA to NaHA as also HyA to HA is attributed as due to the relative flexibility in structure and ease of availability of functional groups¹¹ for complexation. Use of fly-ash in such system enhances the flocculation capacity through the formation of ash organic matter and ash-clay adsorption complex. Moreover, this helps to remove residual organic load that might ultimately invite bacterial proliferation. The polyelectrolytic behaviour of these humus salts was verified from the viscometric study n_{sp}/C vs. C in salt free and 0.1 N KCl media in Fig. 1c.

No direct attempt has yet been made to calculate the economy of the coagulation aided by polymeric materials. Indirectly it can be well ascertained in terms of alum reduction: Approximation from laboratory as well as plant scale study reveals that about 1/50th part (at the maximum) of alum dosage can well substitute 50% of actual alum requirement. Again the price of synthetic polymer on an average is 20 times greater than basic alum. Hence, the net saving in this case will more than 50%. In case of humic substances, the cost price largely depends on the economic extraction from humified coal.

TABLE-2 INFLUENCE OF NaHyA, NaHA, NaPAA TOGETHER WITH ASH/ACTIVATED CARBON IN CLARIFICATION OF RIVER WATER IN TERMS OF ALUM REQUIRED/TIME OF CLARIFICATION

Turbidity of water samples in p.p.m.	Alum reqd. to make optimal **coagulation in p.p.m.	**For Optimal coagulation : Alum reqd. with (in p.p.m.)						Time taken for clarification in					
		1.5 mg/ lit. of NaHyA		1.5 mg/ lit. of NaHA		1.5 mg/ lit. of NaPAA		(a)	(b)	(c)	(d)	(e)	(f)
		(a)	(b)	(c)	(d)	(e)	(f)						
		in presence of 50 mg of ash			in presence of active carbon of 100 mg.								
817	36.40	25.00	30.25	21.05	24.76	26.00	19.25	8	10	3	6	9	3
984	35.70	23.50	27.85	21.50	22.25	24.00	19.00	9.5	12	3	8	10	3
1083	42.00	26.00	29.05	25.00	25.00	28.25	20.00	12	15	3	9	10	3
1108	50.80	27.00	31.25	25.50	25.00	29.75	20.25	10	12	3	10	12	3.5
1000	37.80	28.00	33.25	25.85	27.25	31.35	20.50	10	12.5	3.5	10	12	3.5
1600	56.00	45.00	46.50	43.00	43.50	46.00	37.05	10	15	4.5	10	12.5	—
1700	58.00	48.00	50.00	44.50	46.25	49.05	41.25	10	15	4.5	12	15	4.5

* Study was carried out throughout all the representative seasons of the year and an average of 25 samples was taken for each alum dosage fixation.

** Water used were of varied physicochemical characteristics influencing the alum dosage in different seasons

COMPARATIVE INFLUENCE OF NaHyA/NaHA AGAINST HyA/HA IN CLARIFICATION OF RIVER WATER TOGETHER WITH REMOVAL

Turbidity of water samples on p.p.m.	Alum required in p.p.m.	*For Optimal Coagulation : alum reqd. with ash/carbon			
		1.50 mg/lit. of NaHyA (A)	1.50 mg/lit. of NaHA (B)	1.5 mg/lit. of HyA (C)	1.50 mg/lit. of HA (E)
1000	37.80	25.00	30.00	28.90	29.00
1200	45.50	30.00	33.75	35.65	33.00
1400	50.50	33.75		37.00	36.25

OF BACTERIA (COLIFORM ORGANISM) IN CASE OF SOME REPRESENTATIVE SAMPLES OF THE YEAR

** Bacterial population in MPN from 100 ml. × 1000					Bacterial population in MPN per 100 ml. × 1000				
(A)	(B)	(C)	(D)	(E)	(A)	(B)	(C)	(D)	(E)
0.09	0.12	0.20	0.12	0.25	0.05	0.08	0.12	0.09	0.18
0.06	0.08	0.10	0.10	0.12	0.06	0.09	0.08	0.07	0.08
0.15	0.30	0.50	0.40	0.50	0.11	0.20	0.32	0.28	0.24

* An average of 25 samples were taken in each dosage determination.

** Bacterial population in MPN were determined taking average of 20 samples.

Acknowledgement

Two of the authors (SKG and SKN) owe their indebtedness to Dr. G. C. Das, Health Officer, Dr. G. G. Das, Chief Analyst, Calcutta Corporation, Mr. R. Chowdhury, E. E. W. W. (HW), Mr. M. Mandal, Superintendent for their constant encouragement, advice and keen interest in the development work.

References

1. J. A. BEARDSLEY, *J. Amer. Water Wks. Assn.*, 1973, 65, 85.
2. C. DATA, D. Phil. Thesis, Calcutta University, 1968.
3. KUNAL GHOSH and S. K. MUKHERJEE, *Jour. Appl. Polm. Sci.*, 1971, 15, 2073.
4. M. ADHIKARI and S. K. GUPTA, *Science and Culture*, 1975, 41, 248.
5. M. ADHIKARI, S. K. GUPTA and B. BANERJEE, *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1974, 51, 891.
6. M. ADHIKARI, S. K. GUPTA and R. D. BISWAS, *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1975, 53, 127.
7. A. P. BLACK and D. G. WILLEMS, *J. Amer. Water Wks. Assn.*, 1961, 53, 589.
8. J. M. RIDDICK, *J. Amer. Water Wks. Assn.*, 1961, 53, 1007.
9. A. P. BLACK, A. I. BAU, R. A. BONDET and T. M. CAMPBELL, *J. Amer. Water Wks. Assn.*, 1959, 51, 247.
10. D. J. GRENLAND, *Soil Sci.*, 1974, 3, 34.
11. R. W. HAWORTH, *Soil Sci.*, 1971, 3, 71.
12. E. W. TAYLOR, "The Examination of Water and Water Supplier", J. A. Churchill Ltd., London, 7th Edn., 1958.
13. A. Y. HYNDSHAW, *J. Amer. Water Wks. Assn.*, 1972, 64, 91.